

THE IMPACT OF MUARO JAMBI TEMPLE EXISTENCE TO SOCIAL ECONOMY COMMUNITY LIFE, MUARO JAMBI REGENCY

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Abstract

Muaro Jambi Temple is one of tourist attractions which has its own uniqueness, historical heritage and it still looks out of Jambi Province, though it was not free from the previous restoration process. Overtime with the developing of tourism activities of Muaro Jambi Temple, it could give the impact or widespread influence to the community of Muaro Jambi Regency either positive or negative one to the physical surrounding, economic condition, social and community culture around tourist area particularly to the community of Muaro Jambi village. The research aims at 1) knowing the social impact of the existence of Muaro Jambi Temple to the Muaro Jambi village community. 2) knowing the economic impact of the existence of Muaro Jambi Temple to the Muaro Jambi village community. This research uses Descriptive- Qualitative design and the subject of this research was the community of Muaro Jambi village because most of the community depend on their income from Muaro Jambi Temple. Technique of the data collection used three instruments namely; direct observation, interview and documentation. Technique of the data analysis used in this research was descriptive-qualitative interactive model. Based on the findings it can be concluded; 1). the social impact of the existence Muaro Jambi Temple towards the Muaro Jambi Village community are a) There is a good social interaction between traders and traders, traders and the youth, traders and the managers of tourist park as well as traders and the travelers through the two process namely contact and communication social process. b) the social change either positive or negative is the harmony in the community, organization and disorganization between traders and management. 2) The economic impact towards the Muaro Jambi village community with the existence of Muaro Jambi temple are the increase of business opportunity, b) The employment opportunity chance, c) The rise of community economic income of Muaro Jambi village, d) The improvement of the mindset community to become beads craftsmen.

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1. Introduction

Muaro Jambi Temple is a temple complex Buddha shades, even though it consists of some building that affected by Hindu teaching. Buddhism Mahayana Santayana is predicted to be the majority religion which is embraced by most of the community region at that era. That is evidenced by founded many slabs that written "Wajra" at some temples type of Mandala. The position of complex Muaro Jambi temple around the riverbank of Batanghari. The exact position is in the

natural embankment of the river. Complex Muaro Jambi temple contain of temples which are most of the temple still of mound of soil Menapo that not yet supplied. The mound of soil human made like small mountain that named Bukit Segalo or Bukit Perak by the local community.

The temple location is around Muaro Jambi which was built in 4 BC with Melayu Buddha architectural style. Based on Archeology a long time ago, this temple complex was used as central Kingdom ancient. This complex consists of 110 temples which is restore divided 39 groups temples. There is a prediction that temple still contain of temples which is buried around that complex. From 110 temples some of them have restored such as Candi Tinggi 1 and 2, Gumpang Temple, Kedaton Temple, Astano temple, Koto Mahligai, Bukit Segala Temple, etc.

Everyday, the region of Muaro Jambi temple has many visitors from local community. This temple can give positive and negative effect to the community around it, in economic, social and culture lives. The existence of Muaro Jambi temple as culture could open job openings like parking attendant, clothing merchant, cleaning service, craft, food and beverage trade etc. For those reasons, the researchers are interested in conducting a research about the effect of Muaro Jambi Temple existence towards the social economic life of Muaro Jambi village community, Muaro Jambi Distric, Muaro Jambi Regency.

2. Methods

This research is based on field research at 2018 at Muaro Jambi Temple with a descriptive qualitative approach. The technique of data observation and in-depth interview are applied. The information using traders as the key informants. As comparison analysis, this article also used secondary data sources about other villagers. The research question is how the social effect of Muaro Jambi Temple existence to the Society of Muaro Jambi life and the economic effect of the Muaro Jambi Temple.

Figure 1. Social and Economic Effect

Social interdiction can interpret as social dynamist relationship. It means that social interdiction such as relation between one person and another, between one and each other or between group and group personal. There is a symbol in interaction, as a value or give the value to them as the users.

According to Gillin, the meaning of social interaction is social relationship which dynamic that concerned relation between personal in personal with human group. (SoejonoJoekanto, 2012: 55). The supporting factors social interaction like; Imitation, suggestion, identification, sympathy, empathy, and motivation (SolemanTaneko, 2008:65).

Form of social interaction like cooperation, competition and conflict. In term of many characters identify from social interaction form that happened in social life. In words of Gillin and Gillin, form of social interaction is divided into two processes namely associative and dissociative (Sarjonosoekamto, 2005:64). Social interaction on associative has positive character in community life. It means to support someone or a group to get specific purpose. Associative has form such as social contact which contains:

- a. Between person to person
This social contact when a child learn about the habit in the family.
- b. Between person with the human group or on the contrary likes someone feel opposite action with community norm.
- c. Between one human group with the other group. For example two political parties cooperative to beat another political party.

Social control has positive and negative control. Positive social control is social control which lead to teamwork while the negative social control lead to contradiction or even no social control at all. As social human has social encouragement to do the relation with other people, human as social encouragement, Murry point out (Walgito, 2002:57) that human has motive or social encouragement. The human will look for another person to enter relationship or to enter the interaction.

3.Results and Discussions

Basically the tourism can develop at Muaro Jambi Temple because the place has attractiveness to encourage the traveler's come to visit it. Inskeep (1991:77) stated that attractiveness in tourism has 1) natural attraction based on formation natural environment.2) cultural attraction based on human activities involve history, archeology religion and traditional life.3) special types of attraction are artificial such as theme park, circus and shopping.It gives attractiveness to Muaro Jambi Temple as culture attraction. The existence of attractiveness gives the developmentwhich brings positive impact to the society life environment and to the Society Muaro Jambi Village.

The Social Life Impact of the Existence Muaro Jambi Temple to the Muaro Jambi Village Community

All of trader economy social has purpose to fulfill their needs as human that fulfill by their behavior. It pointed out by MiftahToha (2004:38) that every human need can fulfill their personal habit because of someone will be faced with any number of potential necessary. It must fulfill by habit which their choose. The social impact tourist object of Muaro Jambi Temple has impact to the habit of trader social economy, social interaction intertwined between traders also give impact to social economic habit of trader because everyday the trader work and meet another trader so

that it can form social interaction life between traders. As stated by Mr. Adi based on the interview on April 29th, 2018 such as:

My income as beads craftsman in normally around Rp. 50.000 but in holiday, it is more than Rp. 100.000 to Rp.200.000. I don't have side job but my wife has a job as trader here. From my income I can finance my family needs and if there is the rest of the money I usually save it.

The trader behavior in economic cooperation also looks in buy and sell activities which is done everyday by trader. Buying and selling activity is often done between trader, such as ice cube, string of raffia, snack. The trader does this activities because of different needs.

The result of interview, observation and documentation show that the existence of Muaro Jambi Temple as tourist object give the economic impact such as positive impact that increasing widely chance to business, open the employment, increase the income and there is woman emancipation so that the woman can work. There is organization to help the capital problem in business and the volunteer which spend the time as a companion when the visitor come from out side of Jambi or overseas.

Ahok(2018) said that the existence of Muaro Jambi Temple give impact to the society life, it is because appear of the society circle around the temple and appear of small business caused the community look at the chance to do business. Increase the mind set in the trader behavior by develop business trade of trader to more advanced by doing economic cooperation between traders. The existence of Muaro Jambi Temple give social interactive competition in trading the competition between traders at Muaro Jambi Temple in reasonable stage means that the healthy competition without accompanied by treats or violence. Behavior contraction between trader can not avoid at Muaro Jambi Temple that is placement of stalls problem still often be debate among traders. Meanwhile the negative impact from Muaro Jambi temple existence is the garbage that are scattered and stalls are not regular around the temple. The negative effect can do by the manager tourist park of Muaro Jambi Temple. MiftahToha(2004:33)said that behavior is the function from individual interaction eith their environment. The existence of Muaro Jambi Temple also give social impact to the society of Muaro Jambi village in inside social interaction or social change.

The Economic Impact of Muaro Jambi Temple Existence to the Community of Muaro Jambi Village

Based on the research result of economic impact of Muaro Jambi example existence it show that the existence of Muaro Jambi Temple give economic impact to the Muaro Jambi Village. The positive impact in improving community understanding in keep the temple authenticity, increasing widespread in business, open the vocation, increasing income and there is woman emancipation thus the woman can work too(selling) . The negative impact around the temple make broken because of the visitor often go up the temple and mess stalls of the merchant is done by the community.

According to Mr. Ahok(2018) as activist dive young adult around the Muaro Jambi Temple . The problem of place of trade from past problem , there is no special place to the trader, thus the community arbitrarily make merchandise as they wish.

The existence of Muaro Jambi Impact in employment widespread to the community from in terms of behavior, job, customs and many travelers which come help improve he trader or community income. The improvement of trader income originated from many turist buy their product or merchandise. By the improvement of their income can fix the trader income ,finally it will improve welfare and prosperity the traders society of Muaro Jambi Village.In spiteof Muaro Jambi Temple existence the community around the temple still depend their life by fit planting, banana, duku, chilli, durian and vegetables. All this activities to add family income.

4.Conclusion

To sum up, in this paper, the writer conclude: 1) the social impact of Muaro Jambi Temple existence to the Muaro Jambi society: a) drifting good social interaction between traders and traders, traders with young man around the temple, trader with management of tourist park, as well traders with traveler in two processes in social and communication contact. b) social changing in positive as well negative such as the harmony in the community, organization among trader and disorganization. 2) the economic impact of Muaro Jambi Temple existenceto the Muaro Jambisociety : a)increasingly wider opportunities of business, b)open the employment, c) improve the community economic income , d)increasing the society mind set to be the beads craftsmen.

References

- [1] Djam'an Satori dan Aan Komariah, *Metodologi penelitian Kualitatif*, Bandung : Alfabeta, 2010.
- [2] Leonar Y. Andaya, *LEAVES Trade and Ethnicity in the straits of Malaka*) University of Hawai'I press, 2008
- [3] Gillin dan Gillin dalam Soejono Soekanto. (2006). *Sosiologi Suatu Pengantar*. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
- [4] Huberman, Michhel dan Miles, b. Mathwe, (1992). *Analisis data kualitatif*. Jakarta: Universal Indonesia Press.
- [5] Inskoop. (1991). *Tourism Planning, An Integrated and Suitable Development Approach L*.
- [6] Soerjono Soekanto. 2012. *Sosiologi (Suatu Pengantar)*. Jakarta. PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- [7] Sugiyono, *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan Pendekatan Kuantitatif Kualitatif, dan R&D*, Bandun: Alfabeta, 2011.
- [8] Toha, Miftah. 2004. *Perilaku Organisasi Konsep Dasar dan Aplikasinya*. Jakarta : PT. Raja Grafindo Persada

